

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 2.2b

Recommendations on IWG9 R&I activities:
Focus on CO₂ Capture, Target 6

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordination and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

This deliverable is the second installment of D2.2, where the focus is on updating on the process and results of defining new SET-Plan Targets and R&I Actions with focus on CO₂ capture, Target 6.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Author:

Amy Brunsvold

SINTEF Energy Research

2025-02-25

Reviewed by:

María Midón

Zero Emissions Platform

Marie Bysveen

SINTEF Energy Research

Contact details:

+32 2 882 50 07

www.ccus-setplan.eu

www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction.....	4
2	New policy perspectives: the impact of the Net Zero Industry Act and the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy.....	5
2.1	Net Zero Industry Act	5
2.2	Industrial Carbon Management Strategy.....	6
2.3	The role of Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) in the ICMS	7
2.4	The published role of R&I in the ICMS	8
3	Methodology for setting new CO ₂ capture targets and actions.....	10
3.1	Review of CO ₂ capture targets and R&I actions in the previous SET-plan	11
3.2	Overview of CO ₂ capture technologies; status since 2022.....	12
3.3	Barriers to wide-spread deployment and the importance of feedback loops	13
3.4	Survey on next-generation capture.....	14
4	Targets to Deliver Next-generation CO ₂ capture technologies.....	19
4.1	Capture Target 1.....	19
4.2	Capture Target 2: Heat/power sector; with special focus on BECCS.	20
4.3	Capture Target 3: DAC with CCS.....	20
5	R&I needs to reach the CO ₂ capture targets	21
6	Summary.....	24

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Union has set ambitious climate targets, with industrial carbon management emerging as a necessary tool to reach net-zero emissions by 2050. Industrial carbon management is also a strategic opportunity for Europe’s competitiveness, with the EU leading in carbon capture technology development, accounting for over half of global investments in 2023. While challenges related to bringing down the costs, reducing risks, and scaling up remain, R&I investments have been instrumental in overcoming these barriers, enabling technological advancements and building knowledge-sharing initiatives. Consolidating these efforts into a cohesive European framework is essential for accelerating deployment and ensuring long-term sustainability.

The European Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET Plan) plays a pivotal role in this effort, identifying carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilization (CCU) as priority areas (Action 9). Supported by a robust Research and Innovation (R&I) framework, the SET Plan aims to develop the infrastructure, technologies, and policies required to realize Europe’s decarbonization goals.

This report presents recommendations on advancing the **next generation of CO₂ capture technologies** in line with recent policy developments, including the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA) and the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (ICMS). This report evaluates and builds on Target 6 in Figure 1 (established in 2016 and updated in 2020) and identifies new CO₂ capture R&I activities aligned with the ICMS and NZIA.

This process was conducted throughout 2024 and involved a wide range of stakeholders from research, industry, and the public sector. The targets and underlying research and innovation (R&I) needs were developed through various targeted workshops, webinars, meetings with the core working group, bilateral discussions, and an open survey.

50 Mtpa abated by CCS in 2030

Figure 1. SET-Plan targets for 2030 that were last updated in 2021. These targets have been assessed and adapted throughout 2024 to align with the latest policy developments for CCS/CCU in Europe. The red box around Target 6: Capture is the focus of this deliverable.

2 NEW POLICY PERSPECTIVES: THE IMPACT OF THE NET ZERO INDUSTRY ACT AND THE INDUSTRIAL CARBON MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

The Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA) and the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (ICMS) underscore the urgency of scaling up CCS and CCU technologies. These initiatives establish clear benchmarks: achieving a CO₂ storage capacity of 50 million tonnes annually by 2030, expanding to 280 million tonnes by 2040, and 450 million tonnes by 2050. These targets demand significant investments in CO₂ capture, transport, and storage infrastructure, but require a continued focus on R&D to reduce costs and enhance efficiency.

The ICMS introduces a unified approach, emphasizing the need for comprehensive CO₂ value chains that integrate capture, transport, storage, and utilization. By 2040, most CCS/CCU projects are expected to be economically viable, with CO₂ becoming a tradable commodity within the EU. Achieving this vision requires the alignment of national policies, regulatory frameworks, and financial incentives. Furthermore, innovative solutions such as bioenergy with CCS (BECCS) and direct air capture with CCS (DACCS) are gaining traction, driven by initiatives like the Carbon Removal Certification Framework and the Innovation Fund.

2.1 Net Zero Industry Act

The [Net-Zero Industry Act](#) (NZIA) is a significant initiative stemming from the [Green Deal Industrial Plan](#), aimed at boosting the production of clean technologies within the EU. Its main goal is to increase the EU's manufacturing capacity for technologies that support the transition to clean energy, emitting very low or no greenhouse gases during operation. On 6 February 2024, a political agreement was reached between the European Parliament and the Council on the Net-Zero Industry Act, marking a significant step forward. Upon formal adoption, the NZIA will come into effect.

The NZIA aims to attract investments and enhance market access for green technologies in the EU. The objective is for the EU's manufacturing capacity for strategic net-zero technologies to reach around 40% of annual deployment needs by 2030. This will help speed up progress towards the EU's 2030 climate and energy targets and the goal of achieving climate neutrality by 2050. Additionally, it is expected to enhance the competitiveness of EU industries, create high-quality jobs, and contribute to the EU's energy independence.

Regarding CCS, the NZIA seeks to **accelerate the capacity for CO₂ storage** by introducing a first-of-its-kind CO₂ injection capacity target placing unprecedented responsibility on oil and gas producers. While ambitious, it is expected that the proposed NZIA target of **50 million tonnes of annual CO₂ storage capacity by 2030** will require significant funding and will require approximately:

- 3 billion EUR investments in **carbon storage facilities**, depending on the locations and capacity of the geological storage sites.
- 6.2 - 9.2 billion EUR investments in **transport infrastructure** of pipelines and ships.
- 13 – 103 EUR/tonne CO₂ depending on the industry, capture technology and CO₂ concentration in investment costs for **CO₂ capture**. The costs for Direct Air Capture will be significantly higher, between 122 and 530 EUR/tonne CO₂.

- In addition, a report prepared by industry stakeholders for the CCUS Forum estimates a funding shortfall of cumulatively **EUR 10 billion by 2030 for currently announced CCS projects**.

The scale and cost of this challenge is significant and requires a clear strategy to overcome the barriers to widespread CO₂ capture, transport, and storage.

2.2 Industrial Carbon Management Strategy

A unified approach and vision are essential to establish a single market for industrial carbon management solutions, which is crucial for achieving climate neutrality by 2050. This involves creating a supportive business and investment framework, enhancing national policies, and strategically planning infrastructure at the EU level, supported by cooperation between the EU, national administrations, businesses, civil society, and research communities.

The magnitude of this challenge necessitates an EU-wide Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (ICMS) to develop a coherent policy framework that provides regulatory certainty and investment incentives in carbon capture, storage, utilization, and removals. These technologies are essential to achieving climate neutrality and supporting efficient infrastructure investments in transport and storage. To achieve this, Europe must deploy large-scale carbon value chains to support various stages of industrial carbon management.

The ICMS is based on three key technology pathways:

1. **Capturing CO₂ for Storage (CCS):** This involves capturing CO₂ emissions from fossil, biogenic, or atmospheric sources and transporting them for permanent and safe geological storage.
2. **Removing CO₂ from the Atmosphere:** This pathway focuses on capturing biogenic or atmospheric CO₂ and storing it permanently, effectively removing carbon from the atmosphere.
3. **Capturing CO₂ for Utilisation (CCU):** Here, industry uses captured CO₂ in synthetic products, chemicals, or fuels. Initially, this will involve all types of CO₂, but over time, focusing on biogenic or atmospheric CO₂ will provide greater climate benefits.

The EU's strategic objective for 2030 is to develop CO₂ storage capacity of at least **50 million tonnes per year**, along with related transport modes, including pipelines, ships, trains, and trucks, depending on the business case. Initial CO₂ infrastructure hubs and industrial clusters are expected to emerge, supporting CO₂ capture projects with national and EU funding, relying heavily on cross-border CO₂ transport.

According to the strategy, by 2040, most carbon value chains should be economically viable to meet EU climate objectives, with CO₂ becoming a tradable commodity for storage or use within the EU's single market. Up to a third of the captured CO₂ could be utilized. These value chains will require EU-wide transport and storage infrastructure, primarily pipelines, with shipping options available. The infrastructure must enable cross-border transport of captured CO₂ for storage or use, based on regulations ensuring non-discriminatory access to competitive transport and storage services. Capturing hard-to-abate CO₂ emissions in industrial sectors will become standard practice, including all significant remaining sources of industrial process emissions. To meet the 2040 net GHG emission reduction target, biogenic and atmospheric CO₂ capture levels should match and eventually exceed fossil CO₂ capture levels.

Post-2040, industrial carbon management should be integral to the EU's economic system, with biogenic or atmospheric carbon becoming the primary source for carbon-based industrial processes or transport fuels. Any remaining fossil-based CO₂ must be captured, and there should be a strong business case for negative emissions.

2.3 The role of Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) in the ICMS

The ICMS emphasizes the integration of carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies, including Direct Air Capture (DAC) and the capture of biogenic emissions, to achieve climate neutrality by 2050.

It is projected that a total of 50 million tonnes (Mt) of CO₂ should be captured annually from 2030, which is an increase from 34.1 MT proposed in 2023. Of this total, 5.1 Mt are expected to be captured from biogenic sources, such as biomass-based energy production. **Direct Air Capture (DAC):**

This increases dramatically by 2050, it is expected that 450 million tonnes (Mt) of CO₂ are captured. Of this total, XX Mt are expected to be captured from biogenic sources, such as biomass-based energy production.

Direct Air Capture (DAC):

The ICM strategy underscores the importance of scaling up both DAC and biogenic CO₂ capture technologies through supportive policies, financial incentives, and infrastructure development to meet these targets.

Figure 2: Volume of CO₂ captured for storage and utilisation in the EU (above chart) and share of the CO₂ captured by origin (below chart). From the ICMS eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52024DC0062

2.4 The published role of R&I in the ICMS

The ICMS emphasises that investments in research and innovation have had significant effects on improving CCS technologies. From 2007 to 2023, the Commission invested over EUR 540 million in innovative CCUS (Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage) solutions through various research and innovation programs (FP7, Horizon 2020, and Horizon Europe).

As more CCUS projects are set to become operational by 2030, there's value in consolidating these projects into a knowledge-sharing platform. This platform, initiated by the Innovation Fund, aims to gather and disseminate information and best practices among CCUS projects in the EU, focusing on investment decision-making processes, permitting, risk management, and various technical aspects.

In the future, this platform will expand its scope to cover capture technologies, transportation and storage infrastructure, regulatory frameworks, standards, funding opportunities, and stakeholder engagement. It

will remain open to projects willing to share information and collaborate while adhering to competition rules and without disclosing sensitive commercial data.

Lessons learned from industrial projects will inform national and European research and innovation programs to bridge knowledge gaps and accelerate the development of new technologies.

The ICMS highlights the importance of pre-normative research, based on open data. Access to open data is crucial for such research to support standardization components and prevent overly strict limitations.

In the context of the ICMS, the Commission foresees to:

- Support a new collaboration and knowledge-sharing platform for industrial CCUS projects.
- Continue to invest in R&I for industrial carbon management technologies, including energy and cost efficiency optimisation of processes and pre-normative research to contribute to standardisation

However, the ICMS does not describe explicitly the research topics that should be prioritised. This report is thus aimed to provide recommendations on targets and research and innovation actions required for next generation CO₂ capture.

3 METHODOLOGY FOR SETTING NEW CO₂ CAPTURE TARGETS AND ACTIONS

A range of methods have been used to obtain feedback from stakeholders on the R&I targets and actions for CO₂ capture. First, a review of current and complete projects and the list of barriers to widespread CO₂ capture have been reviewed and updated.

The SET Plan working group on Capture has conducted several consultations with relevant stakeholders to identify key R&I priorities for developing next-generation CO₂ capture technologies. This includes

- Workshops in the working group and with stakeholders
- Webinars
- A survey, also circulated on LinkedIn

Table 1. Timeline of information gathering and shaping of the targets

Date	Action/Venue	Goal
22. Feb 2024	ZEP Technical Committee (online)	Present and invite group/individuals to contribute
March, April	Review IMPACTS9 report	Update with information related to projects since the report was launched in 2022.
March, April	IWG9 meetings, Interviews with CO ₂ capture experts around Europe, IWG9	Invite to discussions with selected experts with a set of questions to help review the RD&D activities
20. March	ZEP Meeting (Brussels)	Share status, invite for input
12. April	EERA CCS meeting (online)	Invite for discussion on revised targets, revised R&D needs
June	ZEP Meeting (Brussels)	Provide updated R&I activities and targets for CO ₂ capture to deliver on the SET-Plan, the ICMS, and the NZIA
July – October	IWG9 meetings	Status and recommendations
November and December 2024	Survey circulated on LinkedIn	To get input from wider audience
22. November	EERA Webinar	Share and invite for feedback
5. December 2024	ZEP Meeting (Brussels)	Presented the reports

3.1 Review of CO₂ capture targets and R&I actions in the previous SET-plan

In January 2022, the CCUS SET-PLAN published “Recommendations on the steps required to deliver the R&I activity 6: Developing Next Generation CO₂ Capture Technologies”. This report formed the basis for Target 6 and associated R&I actions in the previous SET-Plan. The report highlights the pivotal role of Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) in achieving climate goals, particularly for hard-to-abate industrial sectors where traditional mitigation measures are insufficient.

Different sectors have varying CO₂ capture needs, with some, like oil and gas, integrating it into their operations, while others rely on funding and incentives. Planned projects in Europe, particularly in the UK, aim to meet climate targets, but more large-scale projects are needed. Technological advancements and cost reductions are essential for next-generation CO₂ capture technologies, which must be validated and deployed at commercial scales. Supporting industrial clusters and developing a stable framework for early movers are also crucial for advancing CCUS deployment.

CO₂ capture technologies have a wide range of maturities and are suitable for different industries but there is no one size fits all solution. The most mature method, using amines and other solvents, operates at high Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) and is commercially viable. Adsorption by solid sorbents can be effective for specific applications, with TRLs ranging from 5 to 9. Oxyfuel combustion, a technology that enables efficient CO₂ capture, has been tested for a variety of applications with TRL ranging from 5-9. Membranes and solid looping are less mature, with TRLs mostly between 5 and 7. Various low TRL technologies such as low-temperature separation, hybrid systems, and fuel cells show promise but require further development.

Direct air capture is estimated to have a TRL of 7-9 and is considered mature as the technology is past the research and development phases, has been validated by a pilot study, and is in the full-scale development phase. However, DAC faces unique challenges due to the low concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere.

The previous 2030 target in the SET-plan related to CO₂ capture is:

“ At least 3 pilots of capture technologies at TRL 7-8 in different industrial applications, including one enabling low-emission hydrogen production. At least 6 pilots of capture technologies at TRL 5-6, of which at least 2 pilots to test climate positive solutions such as Bio-CCS and direct air capture.”

The rationale behind this target was that because several promising technologies for CO₂ capture exist, pilots are needed for these technologies to mature into eventual commercial deployment. There is no "silver bullet", and several pilot technologies should be pursued for various sectors and applications. To reach carbon neutrality as laid out in the European Green Deal, carbon removal solutions are needed, as some sources of CO₂ will remain even beyond 2050. Sustainable capture of bio-based carbon emissions and direct air capture have this potential and is therefore emphasised in the target. The target addresses both the need for a diverse portfolio of technologies and the need for sustainable carbon removal solutions.

The following sections present a review of this target, first by providing an overview of CO₂ capture technologies with the focus on recent pilot and demonstration projects since 2022.

3.2 Overview of CO₂ capture technologies; status since 2022

Below is an overview of several projects and their TRL levels, based on available data.

Table 2: A selection of projects in Europe demonstrating CO₂ capture from TRL 5+

Project	TRL	Country	Industrial applications
Bio-CCS/U	6	CZ	BECCS; CCU
Soletair	6	FI	DACCS; CCU (concrete)
Stockholm Exergi		SE	Energy; BECCS
BioNETzero	5	NO	BECCS, Bio CHP, Oxyfuel combustion, Chemical Looping Combustion
ACCSESS	7	NO	CDR, Pulp and paper, cement, biorefineries, WtE; solvent enzyme post combustion
REALISE	7	NO	Refineries, solvent
Catch4climate	7	DE	Cement; oxyfuel
Cleanker	7	IT	Cement; calcium looping
DMX project	7	FR	Steel; CCS
C4U project	7	BE, NL	Iron and steel; CCS
P2X Kopernikus project	7	DE	Power-to-X
E-CO2MET	7	DE	Methanol production using CO ₂ and hydrogen
HERCCULES	8	IT	Cement; WtE (complete value chain demonstration)
C-Capture	8	UK	Solvent-based technology using a post-combustion capture approach
Novonisis	8	DK	Enzymatic carbon capture
Drax bioenergy carbon capture pilot plant	8	UK	Power; BECCS
HyNet	9	UK	Low carbon hydrogen production

While it is clear that there has been an increase of carbon capture projects since 2021 and many have progressed beyond TRL 5-6, the open literature does not always provide clear economic and technical performances nor provide adequate summaries of the lessons learned, challenges experienced, and achievements of the technologies and it is therefore challenging to assess beyond TRL.

A few technologies have already been demonstrated in relatively large pilot installations. A few more are expected to be confirmed as demonstrated shortly or will be demonstrated within this year.

3.3 Barriers to wide-spread deployment and the importance of feedback loops

It is often the lack of widescale deployment of CCS due to non-technical barriers such as the lack of clear business cases, lack of policies, etc. For full-scale commercial CCS projects to succeed, every component of the value chain must be functional. This includes capturing, transporting, and permanently storing carbon, all of which must be developed and implemented in a coordinated manner. The technology has matured to a point where the entire CCS value chain can now be deployed and operated. However, further optimization and development are necessary to lower costs and reduce the energy penalty and thus technology development and reducing risks and cost remain a priority.

When it comes to **CO₂ capture technology development**, the first challenge is the high cost, and capture facilities require substantial capital investment for deployment and are both energy-intensive and expensive to operate. Costs tend to decrease as technologies become more advanced: in large-scale operations, the cost of CO₂ capture in the power sector has already fallen by 35% since the initial implementations, based on estimates from the International Energy Agency (IEA). However, for heavy industries such as cement production that struggle to meet necessary emission reduction targets, even the priciest technologies can be more cost-effective than other alternatives—or than facing potential shutdowns in a future with stricter regulations.

Another significant challenge is the underperformance—and occasionally complete failure—of CCUS operations, which may be attributed to their relatively early stage of technological development. Many of these issues can be effectively mitigated through increased innovation through research, development, and demonstrations. It is expected that the cost and performance disparities with established technologies will diminish as CCS/CCU deployment becomes more common. The speed of innovation will largely depend on the participation of various stakeholders and the policies that governments implement now.

Substantial public and private investment in research and development is required with a constant focus on exploiting promising results for scale-up and development. As knowledge and expertise grow, the market will expand, and economies of scale will help reduce costs, similar to the solar photovoltaic industry's development.

Moreover, once these technologies become widespread, governments should consider making CCS mandatory for the most polluting industries. The Net Zero Industry Act and Industrial Carbon Management Strategy are good starting points and can allow companies to start preparing operationally and financially and incorporating future climate legislation requirements into their budgets and long-term business plans.

Feedback loops between industrial projects and research and development (R&D) in CO₂ capture are crucial for accelerating innovation, improving efficiency, and reducing costs.

R&D often develops CO₂ capture technologies under controlled laboratory conditions or simulations. When these technologies are implemented in industrial projects, real-world challenges such as scale-up issues, material degradation, or process inefficiencies emerge. Feedback from industrial projects helps researchers refine models, optimize materials, and improve process designs to make them more robust and practical.

Industrial projects generate large volumes of operational data that can reveal unexpected performance trends, bottlenecks, or degradation mechanisms. R&D teams can analyze this data to develop new solutions, adjust assumptions, and iterate on technology improvements more rapidly than relying solely on theoretical studies. Feedback from early-stage demonstration projects informs R&D efforts on how to address scaling challenges, ensuring smoother transitions from pilot to commercial deployment.

Real-world deployment of CO₂ capture technologies provides insights into operational costs, maintenance needs, and energy consumption. This helps R&D focus on areas that will yield the greatest cost reductions.

Industries are often hesitant to adopt new CO₂ capture technologies due to financial and operational risks. A strong feedback loop ensures that lessons from early adopters lead to more reliable, validated, and bankable solutions, increasing confidence among investors and policymakers.

Without continuous feedback loops, R&D efforts risk developing solutions that are impractical or too expensive for industrial use. By integrating insights from real-world CO₂ capture projects, researchers can refine technologies to be more efficient, scalable, and cost-effective—ultimately accelerating the path to widespread CCS deployment.

3.4 Survey on next-generation capture

A survey was developed and circulated in November 2024 to gauge the CO₂ capture community's opinions and recommendations related to the SET-Plan targets. The survey was posted on LinkedIn on the EERA CCS JP page and reposted by SINTEF. The survey was also emailed to various mailing lists. However, we reached only 26 people who filled out the survey, and of these, only 6 people left comments.

Below are examples of the results of the survey.

Survey: CO₂ capture technologies

We are gathering expert input to refine and set new targets for CO₂ capture technologies as part of the ongoing efforts under the CCUS SET-Plan. We understand that CCS relies on the success of the entire value chain from capture to transport to storage, but we ask for your input specifically on CO₂ capture with this survey.

Your insights will help shape the next phase of research and development, advancing Europe's pathway to climate neutrality. Please take a moment to share your feedback.

1. Please select the R&D challenges/aspects for CO₂ capture in Industrial Sectors (select all that apply): *

- Small-scale emitters
- Tailor-made capture for different emitters
- Low-concentration emitters (below 5% CO₂)
- Robust, capture-ready industrial process design
- Enabling synergies in industrial clusters – explore circular economy, industrial symbiosis
- Develop technologies that control emissions
- Low TRL technologies are still needed, all the way to high TRL

Figure 3. Opening page of the Survey on CO₂ capture technologies developed to gauge the development of updated SET-Plan targets.

Please select the R&D challenges/aspects for CO₂ capture in Industrial Sectors (select all that apply):

Can you describe additional R&D challenges for CO2 capture in industrial sectors?

6 Responses

ID ↑	Name	Responses
1	anonymous	EU funds R&D taylor-made for creating competition, rather to ensure deployment. This leads to projects with extreme focus on technology development while technology for capture already exists from multiple vendors.
2	anonymous	Solvent degradation and emission mitigation
3	anonymous	Improve the overall energy efficiency of the capture process
4	anonymous	Pilot testing with non-proprietary technology and making the research available to all
5	anonymous	Process intensification, e.g. by combining functionality or removing mass and heat transfer resistance, can bring down cost of capture. Specific technology (potentially integrated) needs to be developed for achieving CO2 specs at acceptable costs.
6	anonymous	Cost and Energy are the challenges

Which Industrial sectors need pilots at TRL 7-8 before 2030 (select all that apply):

Which Industrial sectors need pilots at TRL 5-6 before 2030 (select all that apply):

- Iron 2
- Steel 1
- Cement 1
- Pulp and Paper 4
- Hydrogen Production 1
- Metallurgy 4
- Refineries 3
- Other - specify 0
- Other 1

Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS): BECCS has emerged as a critical technology for carbon-negative solutions. In addition to the challenges outlined for industrial CCS in question 1, the following are seen as remaining challenging (select all that apply):

- Energy- and cost-efficient integration of biomass feedstock conversion with CO2 capture for a range ... 4
- Scaling up requirements and pathways, what feedstocks to use, where to use them, and how to... 3
- Feedstocks (sustainability, location to use, etc.) 2
- Small to medium emitters and the logistics around that 4

- Reducing energy requirements and integrating low-cost, low-carbon energy... 4
- Improving material performance to capture CO2 at a greater capacity, with longer... 4
- Improving CO2 capture and desorption kinetics 3
- Reducing potential environmental impacts 1
- Other - specify 0
- Other 1

Please describe additional R&D challenges for CO2 capture in BECCS applications.

6 Responses

ID ↑	Name	Responses
1	anonymous	Competitive use of biomass as feedstock for other applications. Ethical aspects of BECCS (greenwashing while oil and gas keeps being a strong industry).
2	anonymous	Modular process design
3	anonymous	Development and demonstration of compact and simple in operation technologies for small scale decentralized applications
4	anonymous	Understanding the importance of different types of feedstocks and impurities impacts on the technology performance through piloting for at least 6 months in a single project
5	anonymous	Purification
6	anonymous	Cost reduction and new absorption technology

1. Research Infrastructure Needs: How can research infrastructures, like ECCSEL, be better oriented toward supporting Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) technologies such as Bio-CCS and DAC?

6 Responses

ID ↑	Name	Responses
1	anonymous	N/D
2	anonymous	More input from industry
3	anonymous	Integttate and provide access facilities for testing and evaluation of novel technologies in application relevant environment.
4	anonymous	It should be mandatory for all projects to use Eccsel to perform tests to receive funding
5	anonymous	High-throughput screening of adsorbents Use of fieldlabs for testing integrated systems
6	anonymous	Need more research

4 TARGETS TO DELIVER NEXT-GENERATION CO₂ CAPTURE TECHNOLOGIES

Next-generation CO₂ capture technologies are essential for meeting European climate targets. Immediate actions are needed to scale up projects, advance technological readiness, and create conducive policy environments. Collaboration among stakeholders and leveraging lessons from existing projects will be critical to success.

Based on the previous sections in this report and the methodology used in Section 3, it is clear that to meet the European climate objectives for 2030, more commercial-scale CCUS projects must become operational quickly. While commercial technological solutions exist and need deployment, ongoing technological development is crucial to reduce CCS costs and energy demands, enhancing its appeal as an emissions reduction method. Developing next-generation CO₂ capture technologies will involve various validation steps, from pilot testing to commercial scaling. Leveraging accumulated experience from existing capture technologies will be invaluable for advancing these new technologies and promoting CCUS deployment in Europe.

Next generation CO₂ capture technology development is thus recommended across three 2030 targets to reflect the updated policy landscape and increased scale and speed needed to reach climate targets. It is critical that lessons learned from pilots and industrial projects should inform national and European research and innovation programs to bridge knowledge gaps and accelerate the development of new technologies.

Figure 4. Three targets for CO₂ capture in the revised SET-Plan. These three targets are recommended as an update to replace Target 6 in the previous SET-Plan. More details can be found below.

4.1 Capture Target 1

At least eight pilots of promising CO₂ capture technologies at TRL7-8 across industrial sectors WtE, iron & steel, cement & lime, pulp & paper, hydrogen production, metallurgy, refineries. Additionally, 10+ pilots at TRL 5-6 will be needed to mature promising novel technologies.

Description

For CO₂ capture technology development, industrial sources of CO₂ can have very different characteristics, different CO₂ concentrations, impurities in the flue gas, intermittency, etc and the technology development will evolve significantly as the larger scale networks and transport infrastructure comes online. For hard to abate industries, and because their characteristics are quite broad, there is an immediate need to pilot and demo as many technologies as possible across the industrial sectors both at higher TRL, and to ensure a steady pipeline of technologies developed at lower to mid TRL as well.

Therefore, while the short-term focus should remain on wide spread deployment, there is a pressing need to increase support for R&D, from innovative new ideas to testing and piloting new technologies, and to bring forward technologies and solutions that have techno-economic potential to the market. And at the same time again to ensure that the learnings are shared at every level to keep the innovation feedback loop in constant motion. Experiences, Learnings, and outcomes, successes and failures, should be openly shared so that projects can build upon each other to maximize learnings.

This should lead to the development of CO₂ capture ready solutions for a suite of hard-to-abate industries and reduce the time from piloting to the market. Fit-for-purpose solutions should be explored for a variety of sectors across many regions in Europe.

4.2 Capture Target 2: Heat/power sector; with special focus on BECCS.

At least 4-6 pilots at TRL7-8 on CO₂ capture in the heat/power sector; with special focus on BECCS. Additionally, 10+ pilots at TRL 5-6 will be needed to mature promising novel technologies.

Description

Provide improved and sustainable solutions for CO₂ capture in the power sector; including BECCS and relevant/remaining fossil-based power applications. Bio based heat and power and combined heat and power.

4.3 Capture Target 3: DAC with CCS.

At least two pilots at TRL 7 for DAC solutions and four pilots at TRL4-6. CCU for value chains where CO₂ is permanently stored.

Description

Scaling up DAC to remove substantial CO₂ amounts from the atmosphere presents a significant hurdle. Establishing pilot, demo, and large-scale DAC facilities capable of capturing gigatons of CO₂ annually demands substantial investments, infrastructure enhancement, and optimization of capture materials and processes.

Provide improved DAC solutions that improve energy requirements and costs of capture, have the significant potential for scale up, and integrate renewable energy.

5 R&I NEEDS TO REACH THE CO₂ CAPTURE TARGETS

The following topics were identified as key to enable CO₂ capture at the level required to meet climate goals:

Activity 1: Improve the technical performance of CO₂ capture to improve energy efficiency, reduce costs, and reduce risks

Identified gaps given the new policy landscape and description of the new R&I activities

To meet the European climate objectives for 2030 and to reach the ambitions of the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy towards 2040 and 2050, more commercial-scale CCUS projects must become operational quickly. While commercial technological solutions exist and need deployment, ongoing technological development is crucial to reduce capture costs and energy demands. Developing next-generation CO₂ capture technologies will involve various validation steps, from validation of ideas, through pilot and demonstration testing of promising ideas, to commercial scale-up in promising value chains. There is no "silver bullet", and several pilot technologies should be pursued for various sectors and applications. Leveraging accumulated experience from existing capture technologies will be invaluable for advancing these new technologies and promoting industrial carbon management deployment in Europe.

Overarching R&I activities to improve the technical performance of CO₂ capture should address aspects of the following:

- Energy Efficiency and Compatibility: Ensure CO₂ capture process energy requirements align well with industrial applications and available heat and power sources. Prioritize technology development considering access to clean and sustainable energy sources. Explore potentials for using bio-based feedstocks in industrial processes can lead to carbon dioxide removal pathways
- Improved technical designs and operations to lower cost and energy requirements: Emphasize flexibility, compactness, and potential for heat integration and process intensification in technological advancements. Advance novel reactor designs, modularization, and cost-effective materials to reduce both CAPEX and OPEX. Develop a portfolio of large projects at varying Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) to drive down costs and reduce risks.
- Emissions Control, Safety, Quality Assurance: Address emissions control (e.g. solvent and material degradation to air) and health, safety, and environmental considerations early in technology development to facilitate commercialization. Ensure that new technologies and materials do not create new environmental concerns or problem shifting. Ensure next-generation CO₂ capture technologies maintain industrial production/process quality and continuity through technology qualification processes. Avoid technologies that create problem shifting.
- Industrial Clustering: Support the formation of industrial clusters to encourage energy integration, infrastructure sharing, and risk mitigation among partners.

Activity 2: CO₂ capture solutions for negative emissions technologies

Identified gaps given the new policy landscape and description of the new R&I activities

Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) solutions are needed, are needed, as some sources of CO₂ will remain even beyond 2050. However, a clear framework for carbon accounting must be developed further. In the industrial carbon management context, this will include direct air capture with CCS (DACCS), bioenergy with CCS (BECCS), and bio-based industrial processes (more broadly called bio-CCS) such as e.g. pulp and paper, co-firing of biomass in cement kilns, and biochar for metallurgical industries. For all bio-based processes it is crucial to select sustainable solutions and to understand the full value chain from which feedstocks to use, how to use them, where to use them, and how to transport and store the CO₂. The scale of the challenge is at an all-time high and both commercial scale projects and R&I efforts should increase

Bioenergy with CCS (BECCS)

Ensuring the sustainability of biomass feedstocks for energy production is crucial. Research is needed to assess the environmental and social impacts of large-scale biomass cultivation and harvesting, including land use change, biodiversity loss, competition with food production, and other negative environmental impacts.

Improving the efficiency of carbon capture technologies is essential to maximize CO₂ removal from biomass combustion emissions. Research is needed to develop and optimize capture technologies suitable for biomass power plants, considering factors such as flue gas composition and variability. R&D is needed on the overall carbon footprint of biomass production, transporting, processing and through conversion.

Enhancing the efficiency of biomass-to-energy conversion processes is critical for maximizing energy yields and minimizing emissions. Research challenges include developing advanced conversion technologies and improving the efficiency of existing combustion processes.

Integrating BECCS into existing energy infrastructure requires overcoming technical, economic, and regulatory barriers. Optimizing the integration of BECCS systems with existing energy infrastructure and grid systems is essential for maximizing overall efficiency and minimizing costs. Research challenges include developing integrated modelling frameworks to assess the techno-economic feasibility and environmental impacts of BECCS deployment at various scales.

Addressing policy and socio-economic barriers to BECCS deployment is crucial for its widespread adoption. Research is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of policy instruments and to assess public perceptions and acceptance of BECCS technology and its feedstock sustainability.

In addition to the more generic R&I activities described in Activity 1 related to energy efficiency, flexibility, reduced costs, and safety, the following R&I activities BECCS technologies are thus prioritised:

- Emissions, air pollution control, contaminants,
- Develop processes that integrate biomass feedstocks in industrial processes with CO₂ capture. – examples such as in **pulp and paper, include co-firing of biomass in cement kilns, biochar in metallurgical and silicon production, etc.**
- Develop modular solutions, including small-scale.

Direct Air Capture – (DAC)

Due to the low concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere, in most cases, DAC will be more expensive to capture CO₂ from the air than industrial flue gases with CO₂. However, it is imperative to decrease the energy intensity required to enhance its economic viability and sustainability.

Scale-up Challenges: Expanding the technology to remove substantial CO₂ amounts from the atmosphere presents a significant hurdle. Establishing large-scale DAC facilities capable of capturing gigatons of CO₂ annually demands substantial investments, infrastructure enhancement, and optimization of capture materials and processes.

Environmental Considerations: The energy source used in DAC, often fossil fuels, poses environmental concerns by releasing additional CO₂ and pollutants. This offsets the benefits of carbon capture. Therefore, integrating renewable energy sources into DAC systems is crucial to minimize their overall environmental impact.

The following R&I activities for DAC are thus prioritised:

- Develop viable baselines for DAC that can serve as the basis for technology comparison.
- Reducing energy requirements and integrating low-cost, low-carbon energy sources.
- Improving material performance to capture CO₂ at a greater capacity, with longer lifetimes.
- Improving CO₂ capture and desorption kinetics.
- Reducing potential environmental impacts.

Activity 3: CO₂ capture in hard-to-abate industries

Identified gaps given the new policy landscape and description of the new R&I activities

Industrial carbon management is critical to reach European climate targets and, in many cases, CCS is the decarbonisation pathway for hard-to-abate industries. Flue gases, which are the byproducts of combustion in various industrial processes, can vary significantly depending on the industrial sector. The composition and characteristics of these gases are influenced by the type of fuel used, the combustion process, and the specific industrial activity and lead to varying levels of CO₂ concentration and level of impurities. Understanding these differences is crucial for designing effective CO₂ capture and emission control technologies tailored to each sector's specific needs.

Suggested R&I activities include:

- Tailor-made capture and capture integration for different emitters, including a range of scales of emitters. A portfolio of technologies is needed, from low TRL technologies where promising solutions move to piloting and demonstrations.
- Develop solutions for low-concentration emitters (CO₂ concentration below 5%)
- Develop robust, capture-ready industrial process design and find synergies with the core industrial process and CO₂ capture.
- Blue hydrogen demonstrations needed.
- Enabling synergies in industrial clusters – Support the formation of industrial clusters to encourage energy integration, infrastructure sharing, and risk mitigation among partners. Explore industrial symbiosis in clusters.
- Energy- and cost-efficient integration of biomass feedstocks for industrial processes conversion with CO₂.

6 SUMMARY

This report is part of a Horizon Europe project aimed at supporting stakeholders involved in Carbon Capture, Utilisation, and Storage (CCUS) through the European Technology Innovation Platform for Zero Emissions (ETIP ZEP) and the SET-Plan Implementation Plan Working Group 9 (IWG9). The primary goal is to align and coordinate CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities to advance Europe's climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

Key Focus Areas:

- **Policy Alignment:** Examining the impact of the Net Zero Industry Act (NZIA) and the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy (ICMS) on CCUS deployment.
- **CO₂ Capture Technologies:** Reviewing existing and emerging capture technologies, barriers to large-scale implementation, and necessary R&I actions.
- **Updated SET-Plan Targets:** Refining the CO₂ capture targets to accelerate the development of next-generation technologies, focusing on:
 - CO₂ capture in hard-to-abate industries (e.g., cement, steel, waste-to-energy).
 - CO₂ capture in the power sector, particularly Bioenergy with CCS (BECCS).
 - Direct Air Capture with CO₂ Storage (DACCS).
- **Research and Innovation Priorities:** Addressing technical and economic challenges to improve energy efficiency, reduce costs, and enhance the scalability of capture technologies.